

ISic2816

I.Sicily inscription 2816

Language

Oscan

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Museo regionale

interdisciplinare di Messina, inventory 239 + 241

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 171041

Bibliography

Crawford, M.H. 2011. *Imagines Italicae. A Corpus of Italic Inscriptions. Bulletin of the Institute of Classical Studies Supplement 111*. London. At Messina 5

Parlangèli, O. 1956. Le iscrizioni osche (mamertine) di Messina. *Bollettino Centro di Studi Filologici e Linguistici Siciliani*. 4: 28-38. At no.1.B

Orioles, V. 1992. Bilinguismo e biculturalismo nella Messina mamertina. *Studi linguistici e filologici offerti a Girolamo Caracausi*. Palermo. pp. 331-345.

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